

VALUE CHAIN GENERATOR

Maja Berden Zrimec, Mateja Dermastia, Miha Škrokov, Gašper Božič,
Veronika Levak, Mateja Novak, Jon Goriup Dermastia

Anteja ECG, Slovenia

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10006736
jon@vcg.com

Abstract: *The circular bioeconomy can significantly reduce waste and lower the need for mining of primary new materials, but many companies are unable to find and connect with businesses that can utilize their bioresources. In this context, VCG.ai plays a vital role. The Value Chain Generator (VCG) is a digital solution that matches companies based on their resources, including waste, within the scope of the circular bioeconomy. Leveraging artificial intelligence, big data, and machine learning, VCG empowers clusters, business support organizations, and companies to explore and develop new value chain designs, fostering knowledge transfer and enhancing overall knowledge in this economic field. It also connects stakeholders in the regions and beyond.*

VCG finds unexploited business opportunities for bio-based value chains based on available data to overcome the existing information gaps. It matches companies according to their resources, including waste, and on established good practices in value chain design. New value chain designs are done by matching production inputs and outputs across industrial sectors. VCG also provides a knowledge transfer network by facilitating the sharing of good (bio)links with other clusters and organisations to increase the overall knowledge. The good practices shared within the system can be applied to individual companies, enabling them to find the right partners to implement selected circular value chain models.

For example, in a new circular business model, waste, particularly bio-waste, can be transformed into bio-plastics through a process of bioconversion or chemical recycling, offering a sustainable alternative to traditional, petroleum-based plastics. This approach not only gives a second life to waste materials, reducing landfill and environmental pollution, but also aids in the creation of a circular economy, where waste is viewed as a valuable resource not as an endpoint.

Keywords: circular economy, bioeconomy, value chains, bioresources

1 INTRODUCTION

Every year, agri-food value chains waste staggering amounts of resources - equivalent to one-third of all food produced for human consumption – culminating in a severe environmental problem (Searchinger et al., 2018). The repercussions are far-reaching, with annual food loss & waste emerging as the world's third largest emitter, trailing only behind the entire economies of the US and China. The financial burden is equally significant, with the industry incurring tens of billions of euros annually in Europe alone (Poore & Nemecek, 2018)).

At this pivotal moment, governments and industries are investing billions into climate solutions, and companies are committing to science-based targets and climate goals. We stand on the threshold of a transformative wave where sustainable practices will shape the future of business. The global market for new circular products from agri-food value chains is projected to reach over 2.6 trillion € by 2030 (WBCSD, 2020). Alongside the growing pressures for sustainability, this presents a compelling financial incentive for companies to explore circular solutions and diversify their business. Many companies are working hard to change their business in the hope of getting additional value streams and becoming less vulnerable to the changes we are facing. Various studies imply that reorganising value chains is imperative to make them more resilient (CIRAIG, 2015). And while the world is turning to the circular economy, and bioeconomy to become more sustainable, companies are having trouble making the necessary changes. Circular business models enable a step towards these objectives (Hansen & Revellio, 2020). Nevertheless, it is a challenge for them to find compatible actors in the newly created value chains. Many companies have abundant bioresources that could be further utilised for new products or services but have trouble finding and connecting with a business that could take advantage of their resources. On the other hand, a company might be searching for bioresources and wouldn't know where to turn.

1.1 Value creation

The value chains needed to create business between companies in the scope of circular bioeconomy are in many cases completely missing. Companies are still trapped in the linear way of thinking, where the value creation is straight forward and end-of-life for the product is waste disposal or, at best, recycling of its parts.

Business models in a circular economy offer a wider selection of value creation approaches than in linear value chains. The reason is that instead of simply

relying on consumption, value is created based on the use (CIRAIG, 2016). Circular business models support the prolonged lifetime of a product by following the 4R principle of repairing, reusing, remanufacturing, and recycling (Tapaninaho & Heikkinen, 2022). Focus is shifted from a single use cycle to resource recovery and multiple use cycles to preserve the value of the products, materials, and parts as long as possible. Additional life cycles are created to enable even more possibilities for valorisation. Consequently, waste is reduced or used as a secondary raw material, which in turn reduces the need for mining of primary new materials.

To achieve multiple value creation, a number of stakeholders from various circular economy system levels must work together in a collective and interorganisational way (Tapaninaho & Heikkinen, 2022). New and diverse value networks for cycling resources and parts must be created. Value chain actors must collaborate to secure viable links between them, for example, to deliver a constant quality and quantity of secondary raw materials (SRMs). SRMs are technically the materials that can be recycled and then injected back into the economy as new raw materials (European Commission, 2015). They are typically obtained either from production waste or from End-of-Life products, sent to recycling plants at the end of their lifespan (RMIS).

1.2 Digital tools

Circular economy has already gained a very important place in EU politics. Consequently, many countries have adopted accompanying regulations and tax measures, for example, to support repair and reuse of products instead of disposing and recycling their parts. The policy is also trying to extend the warranty period for products to discourage their low quality and short-term usage. Boosting the circular economy plan in EU, supported by the Commission's EU Circular Economy Action Plan (March 2020), includes measures along the entire life cycle of products promoting circular economy processes, fostering sustainable consumption, and guaranteeing less waste. The focus is currently on the food chain, textiles, packaging and plastics, construction and buildings, batteries and vehicles, electronics, and ICT.

To enable the necessary changes for the transition to a circular economy, technological development is one of the crucial drivers. New technologies will enable the circulation of energy and materials, improve resource efficiency and utilisation of secondary raw materials, including what has been until recently considered as waste. Digitalisation plays a very important role in this scenario as the digital environment supports a broad range of platforms that connect suppliers to producers.

Underdeveloped or non-existing technology is currently an important barrier that can hinder company's ability to adopt the circular approach. It may not be technically possible to reuse, refurbish, or remanufacture existing products to meet current performance demands. Concerns also exist about the technical performance properties of recovered and recycled materials.

While circular business models' goal is to replace primary production and enable environmental sustainability, there can be situations when circular offerings do not deliver environmental benefits. For example, recycling and remanufacturing of products can be very energetically demanding. Circularity thus doesn't inherently imply sustainability and must be actively driven in this direction. Companies therefor need a system that not only establishes circular value streams but enables them to evaluate the outcomes of various circular solutions.

2 METHODS

In the face of increasing sustainability demands, VCG.AI offers a transformative solution. Our pioneering AI & big data platform is designed to convert waste in bio-based value chains into lucrative circular opportunities. By analyzing companies' production processes and local industries' material flow data, the platform aligns with various mandatory and voluntary circular economy reporting standards, addressing the challenges many companies face due to decentralized data on their material and waste streams.

Central to VCG.AI's methodology is the BioLink models, a smart matching system that seamlessly connects businesses with the right technology, service, and supply chain partners. Our platform's strength is derived from its proprietary database and unique matching engine, which pinpoints high-potential circular solutions for companies and suggests prospective partners for implementation. Integrated with the widely-used ERP system, Oracle, VCG.AI ensures that businesses are expertly paired with the most efficient circular solutions and partners, setting the stage for a sustainable and profitable future.

Figure 1. An example of building new value chain with VCG.ai.

3 CASE STUDIES

3.1 Bioplastics from Organic Waste

Bioplastics, as alternatives to conventional petroleum-derived plastics, have garnered significant attention due to their potential to mitigate global pollution concerns. Derived primarily from renewable sources, these bio-based and/or biodegradable materials can be produced using various feedstocks, including agricultural residues and food waste. Organic waste, especially food waste, represents a significant fraction of the municipal solid waste stream (Gustavsson et al., 2011). These organic waste streams are a rich source of carbon and can be converted into high-value products such as bioplastics through biological or chemical processes (Kourmentza et al., 2017).

Acquavia et al. (2021) highlighted the utilization of fruit and vegetable wastes as raw materials for bioplastics production, emphasizing the potential of these waste sources to be converted into biomaterials through both simple and complex processes. Gröndahl et al. (2021) further explored the promise of lignocellulosic biomass from agricultural and industrial waste sources, particularly focusing on nanocellulose production from non-wood waste sources and its diverse applications.

The conversion process typically involves hydrolysis of organic waste to fermentable sugars, which are then converted into lactic acid or polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) using specific bacteria in a fermentation process (Chen, 2009). These bioplastics can be used in a variety of applications, including packaging, agriculture, and medicine (Avérous & Pollet, 2014).

3. 2 Breweries residues as a resource

The food and beverage industry is increasingly focusing on sustainable practices and circular economy principles to mitigate environmental impacts. Breweries produce a large amount of waste or residues that still contain significant amounts of nutrients and minerals, including carbohydrates, proteins, fibers, and fat. To produce 100 L of beer, around 20 kg of waste is generated (Adams et al., 2022). Traditionally, these by-products have been used as animal feed or disposed of in landfills (Biala et al., 2017). However, their use is much wider, encompassing the production of high-value products like PHA or extracting enzymes, polyphenols, antioxidants, and various chemical compounds (Ganeva et al., 2020; Cimini & Moresi, 2021; Cuomo et al., 2022).

To become truly circular, several challenges have to be overcome. For example, the high moisture content of Barley Spent Grain makes it prone to microbial spoilage, thus it is challenging to transport it to other processing sites (Cuomo et al., 2022). Costs for drying BSG greatly increase the price of the dried product compared to analogous conventional lignocellulose residues (Cimini & Moresi, 2021).

Recently, the bioconversion of brewery waste into high-value products using insects has emerged as a sustainable alternative. Black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) and the common housefly (*Musca domestica*) are among the insects found to be effective in converting organic waste into protein-rich biomass (Cickova et al., 2015). The insect-derived protein can be used as a sustainable alternative to fishmeal or soy in animal feed, which has the potential to alleviate pressures on marine ecosystems and reduce the carbon footprint associated with soy cultivation (Makkar et al., 2014). Frass, as an organic fertilizer, also contributes to sustainable agriculture practices by reducing the dependence on synthetic fertilizers and enhancing soil health (Lalander et al., 2015).

3. 3 Algae as a bridge between companies in circular economy

Algae can be utilized to create a sustainable closed-loop system by treating wastewater, reducing pollution, and producing biomass (Mohsenpour et al., 2021; Berden Zrimec et al., 2020). Algae cultivation in wastewater offers oxygenation benefits, and the harvested biomass can be used for various applications, reducing the need for energy-intensive treatment processes. In biogas plants, algae can stabilize the liquid phase of anaerobic digestate (Figure 2), which is rich in nutrients, reducing storage, transportation costs, and greenhouse gas emissions (Berden Zrimec et al., 2023; Rossi et al. 2023; Bauer et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Circularity in biogas plants with algal systems (source: Algen, algal technology center, llc (www.algaebiogas.eu)).

Macroalgal biomass can be stabilized through composting or pyrolysis for agricultural use (Cole et al., 2016). Composting uses algae as a nitrogen source, while pyrolysis converts it into biochar, which enhances soil quality, nutrient retention, and promotes soil microbiota. The algal biomass is also rich in amino acids, fatty acids, and vitamins, making it an ideal raw material for a biorefinery approach to produce biofuels, bioplastics, cosmetics, and aquafeed, among other products (Tawfik et al., 2022).

Algae can also be integrated into existing technological systems without requiring major structural changes, making them attractive for industries. They can be added to wastewater treatment systems or industrial technologies as side-streams (Mohsenpour et al., 2021; Oviedo et al., 2022). For instance, algae raceway ponds can reduce the production of sludge in wastewater treatment.

For the successful implementation of algae cultivation in wastewater or digestate, innovative business models are essential (Bauer et al., 2021; Lawton et al., 2017). These include producing algae for specific industries, developing integrated systems for wastewater treatment and resource recovery, forming circular economy partnerships, generating carbon credits, and creating direct-to-consumer products. These models can help in creating sustainable and profitable businesses while contributing to a circular bioeconomy.

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